

Perceptions of The Social Effects of Coronavirus Among the Inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract:

This study investigated the perceptions of the social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria. The descriptive survey research design was used in this study. The population consisted of adults above 18 years in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 1,500 adults selected from Southwest, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select the sample for the study. A self-designed questionnaire tagged "Social Effect of Coronavirus Questionnaire (SECQ)" was used to collect relevant data for the study. The face and content validity of the instrument were ascertained by specialists in the field of Social Science and Tests & Measurements who eliminated all irrelevances and ambiguous items. The reliability co-efficient value of 0.832 obtained was considered statistically high to make the instrument reliable and useable. The data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that the perceived social effects of Coronavirus are physical separation, increase in rate of unemployment, increase in rate of poverty, increase in domestic violence, increase in sexual abuse and rape, and reduction in quality of social relationship. In addition, the perceived social effects of Coronavirus differ based on gender but no difference in their perceptions based on age and marital status. It

EASIJ

Accepted 25 August 2020

Published 31 August 2020

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4013299

was recommended among others that the Government should provide palliatives for different sectors of the economy as this can go a long way to reduce poverty and unemployment.

Keywords: Perceptions, Social Effects, Coronavirus,

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Introduction

Coronavirus also known as COVID-19 is a novel disease that has no cure yet. It originated from Wuhan in China and has since then crossed continents and became a pandemic. It is caused by the coronavirus a family of SARS-Cov-2, the commonest symptoms are fever, dry cough and tiredness while difficulty in breathing, chest pain, loss of speech among others (WHO, 2020a, WHO, 2020b). On average it takes 5-6 days from when someone who is infected with the virus for symptoms to show. The virus is transmitted primarily through respiratory droplets and contacts with infected persons. People with underlying medical conditions like cardiovascular conditions, diabetes, chronic respiratory disease and cancer will develop serious complications if they contract COVID-19. Till date, there is no cure for COVID-19, clinical trials however is ongoing and prevention is the only available way to manage the virus (Azlan, 2020; Thomas, 2020; Baud, Qi, Nielsen-Saines, Musso, Pomar & Favre, 2020; Bhagavathula & Shehab, 2020)

The federal government of Nigeria enforced an initial 2-week lockdown on March 30, 2020, for three of 36 states (Lagos, Ogun, and Abuja) and, on April 13, extended it another 2 weeks before state governments imposed lockdown in their respective states. Shortly after the order was announced by the President Muhammadu Buhari and some state governments, there was uproar among the citizens due to a myriad of concerns, with over 40% of its citizens living below the poverty line. Therefore, a large proportion of the population lives on daily income with no savings to act as a financial buffer during the lockdown. The prospect of staying at home comes with some social implications.

Bhagavathula, Aldhalee, Rahmani, Mahabadi and Bandari (2020) revealed in a survey that loneliness level had increased tremendously, 40% of respondents revealed they are lonely, their relationships are not meaningful and they feel isolated. They also stated that lack of connection heightens health risks and make people more prone to alcohol and smoking. Man are social animals, daily exposure to news about Coronavirus may result in a range of reactions which may be emotional, physical, mental or behavioral. Coping with isolation has brought unprecedented challenge for daily life especially physical separation as a result of social distancing of 2 meters guidelines, no hugs and pats like before but elbow greetings. It is obvious human needs social gathering, social interaction, contacts and connection to survive, if not seen with positive perspective, social distancing may be seen as social isolation (Bhagavathula, Aldhalee, Rahmani, Mahabadi & Bandari, 2020; Renton & Berlinger, 2020).

The researchers observed that schools shut down, offices locked, bars, clubs, sporting activities, tourist attraction sites deserted, religious institutions locked among others has led to reduction in social interaction which invariably may leads to poor mental health outcomes and mortality. Fear about contracting the virus and staying indoors induces anxiety. The researchers also observed that many people lost their jobs in this pandemic as a result of lockdown which led to financial strain. It is no wonder there are reports of escalating mental health problems.

Institutions are shut down and schools are not left out, recently the Federal Government allowed exit classes to resume back in class after schools were disinfected, buckets provided for hand washing with soap and water. Measures of social distancing were ensured and students had their facemasks on, lockers were arranged in zigzag manner and

teachers had face shields and mask on. Hunger was evident because of the shutdown, many who work in private firms had their salaries stopped or divided, small and medium scale enterprises suffered the lockdown, artisans were not left out, though the government shared palliatives but only few benefitted from it.

The researchers also observed that more incidences of rape, social vices and domestic violence are more recorded in this time of Coronavirus due to social isolation. Spouses who only spend few hours together after the long day job are now confined at home and if the relationship between them gets strained, it may result to violence but for spouses with good relationship it is a perfect time for bonding. Other effects of Coronavirus noticed by the researcher are inability for social gathering, sporting events, religious gatherings, clubbing, partying and outdoor games among others.

Based on the above observation, the study investigated the perceptions of the social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

- i. the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria; and
- ii. the difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their gender, age and marital status.

Research Question

This research question was raised to guide the study:

1. What are the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were generated for this study:

1. There is no significant gender difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria
2. There is no significant difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their age
3. There is no significant difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their marital status

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was used in this study. The population consisted of adults above 18 years in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 1,500 adults selected from Southwest, Nigeria. Multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select the sample for the study.

A self-designed questionnaire tagged "Social Effect of Coronavirus Questionnaire (SECQ)" was used to collect relevant data for the study. The instrument consisted of two sections namely: Sections A and B. *Section A* of the instrument sought for comprehensive bio-data of the respondents among which are gender, age, religion and marital status. *Section B* consisted of 10 items which sought information on the social effects of Coronavirus. It was a Yes or No scale.

The face and content validity of the instrument were ascertained by specialists in the field of Social Science and Tests & Measurements who eliminated all irrelevances and

ambiguous items. A pilot study was carried out outside the sampled locations to establish the internal consistency of the instrument. The instrument was administered on 100 respondents and data collected were analysed using Cronbach's alpha which yielded reliability co-efficient of 0.832. The reliability co-efficient obtained was considered statistically high to make the instrument reliable and useable.

The data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research question was answered using frequency counts, percentages and mean. The hypotheses were tested using t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Response Rate

Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Sample Size	1500	-----
Distributed Copies	1500	100%
Retrieved and Valid Copies	1463	97.5 %
Response Rate		97.5%

Table 1 presents the total number of questionnaire copies retrieved from the respondents as well as the response rate achieved. The researcher administered 1500 copies of the questionnaire to the respondents. Out of the 1500 copies of questionnaires administered to the respondents, 1463 were retrieved. It constituted a response rate value of 97.5% which is considered very high and adjudged adequate to be used for further analysis.

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Table 2 Demographic Characteristics

Item		Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Age	18 - 30 years	304	20.8
	31 - 45 years	586	40.1
	46 - 60 years	468	32.0
	61 years and above	105	7.2
	Total	1463	100.0
Marital Status	Married	782	53.5
	Single	449	30.7
	Separated	232	15.8
	Total	1463	100.0
Religion	Christianity	702	48.0
	Islam	697	47.6
	Traditional	64	4.4
	Total	1463	100.0
Gender	Male	571	39.0
	Female	892	61.0
	Total	1463	100.0

Table 2 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents in the study. It can be observed that 304 (20.8%) of the respondent were between 18 – 30 years old, 586 (40.1%) were between 31 – 45 years. The number of respondents in the age bracket of 46 – 60 years was 468 (32.0%) and the number of respondents above 61 years was 105 (7.2%). In terms of marital status, 782 (53.5%) were married and 449 (30.7%) were single. The proportion of those separated was 232 (15.8%). The religious profile revealed that Christian constituted 702 (48.0%) of the sample, Muslim constituted 697 (47.6%), and traditionalist 64 (4.4%). The gender of the respondent showed that Male constituted 571 (39.0%) of the sample while Female were 892 (61.0%).

Descriptive Analysis of Research Question

Research Question 1: What are the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria?

Table 3: Descriptive analysis showing the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus

S / N	ITEMS	N	Yes (%)	No (%)	Mean	Remark
1	Loneliness	1463	659 (45.0%)	804 (55.0%)	1.45	Disagreed
2	Physical Separation	1463	1218 (83.3%)	245 (16.7%)	1.83	Agreed
3	Increase in rate of unemployment	1463	1379 (94.3%)	84 (5.7%)	1.94	Agreed
4	Salary cut	1463	608 (41.6%)	855 (58.4%)	1.42	Disagreed
5	Increase in rate of poverty	1463	927 (63.4%)	536 (36.6%)	1.63	Agreed
6	Increase in domestic violence	1463	998 (68.2%)	465 (31.8%)	1.68	Agreed
7	Increase in sexual abuse and rape	1463	1004 (68.6%)	459 (31.4%)	1.69	Agreed
8	High drugs intake	1463	571 (39.0%)	892 (61.0%)	1.39	Disagreed
9	Reduction in quality of social relationship	1463	1274 (87.1%)	189 (12.9%)	1.87	Agreed
10	Fear of rendering public assistance	1463	544 (37.2%)	919 (62.8%)	1.37	Disagreed

(Mean cut – off: 1.50)

From Table 3, more than half of the respondents perceived that the social effects of Coronavirus are physical separation, increase in rate of unemployment, increase in rate of poverty, increase in domestic violence, increase in sexual abuse and rape, and reduction in quality of social relationship. Increase in rate of unemployment (94.3%) was the most perceived social effect of Coronavirus.

Base on the mean cut – off of 1.50, it can be concluded that the perceived social effects of Coronavirus are physical separation, increase in rate of unemployment, increase in rate of poverty, increase in domestic violence, increase in sexual abuse and rape, and reduction in quality of social relationship.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant gender difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria

Table 4: t-test analysis for gender difference in perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	p-value
Male	571	14.99	1.41	1461	49.023*	0.000
Female	892	18.81	1.52			

*P<0.05

Table 4 shows that the t-cal value of 49.023 is significant because the p-value of 0.000<0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant gender difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their age

Table 5: Analysis of Variance for difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their age

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	5.851	3	1.950	1.137	.329
Within Groups	2501.782	1459	1.715		
Total	2507.633	1462			

P > 0.05

The result presented in Table 5 showed that F_{cal} value of 1.137 was not significant because the P value (0.329) > 0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their age.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their marital status

Table 6: Analysis of Variance for difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their marital status

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4.174	2	2.087	1.411	.302
Within Groups	2159.008	1460	1.479		
Total	2163.182	1462			

P > 0.05

The result presented in Table 6 showed that F_{cal} value of 1.411 was not significant because the P value (0.302) > 0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was

not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their marital status.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that the perceived social effects of Coronavirus are physical separation, increase in rate of unemployment, increase in rate of poverty, increase in domestic violence, increase in sexual abuse and rape, and reduction in quality of social relationship. This finding is similar to the submission of Brooks, Webster, Smith, Woodland, Wesley and Greenberg (2020).

The findings of the study also revealed that there was significant gender difference in perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria. The results revealed that the female respondents perceived differently the social effects of Coronavirus as against the perception of male respondents. However, it was revealed that there was no significant difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their age. This implies that all the respondents have same perception of social effects of Coronavirus irrespective of their age. It was further revealed that there was no significant difference in the perceptions of social effects of Coronavirus among the inhabitants based on their marital status. This implies that inhabitants that are married, single and separated have same perception of the social effect of Coronavirus.

Conclusion

Based the findings of this study, it is concluded that the perceived social effects of Coronavirus are physical separation, increase in rate of unemployment, increase in rate of poverty, increase in domestic violence, increase in sexual abuse and rape, and reduction in quality of social relationship. In addition, the perceived social effects of Coronavirus differ based on gender but no difference in their perceptions based on age and marital status.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. The Government should provide palliatives for different sectors of the economy as this can go a long way to reduce poverty and unemployment.
2. There is need for proper re-orientation on various mass and social media of the essence of abstaining from domestic violence, sexual abuse and other crimes that may be caused by the effect of the pandemic.
3. Government should be firm and fair in its resolution and implementation of decisions to reduce the spread of Coronavirus so that the populace can fully go about their normal life as soon as possible.

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Cite this article:

Author(s), Dr. (Mrs.) AJIBEFUN, Martina Bosede (Ph.D), Dr. (Mrs.) OJO, Grace Ayodele (Ph.D), ASHIBI, Denis Ekpan, (2020). “ Perceptions of The Social Effects of Coronavirus Among the Inhabitants of Southwest, Nigeria”, **Name of the Journal:** Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 95 – 104. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4013299, Special Issue, Issue: 2, Vol.: 2, Article: 10, Month: August, Year: 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

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